

Kosovo*'s ERA Integration

Progress and recommendations

Progress

Coordination of structural reforms in the research sector

- Increased importance of R&I
- Competencies of science, education, technology and innovation bundled in one ministry
- Tenfold increase of R&D budget until 2028 in National Research Programme planned (in comparison to 2022)
- New National Research Council and new National Research Programme established

Increase in R&I output

- Start of development of Smart Specialisation Strategy along Joint Research Centre methodology
- Development of Research Information System for research data and statistics
- Adoption of Research Infrastructure Roadmap and development of data collection register

Participation in European programmes

- First time ever full association to European Framework Programme with Horizon Europe
- Association of the Kosovo Research and Education Network to GÉANT
- Status of COST Near Neighbour Country

*This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Recommendations

Establish a comprehensive R&I approach

- Develop further an integrated R&I policy framework
- Improve coordination and administrative capacities to plan, implement, monitor and evaluate R&I policies comparable to EU procedures and standards
- Interlock R&I legislation and policy to create a better research environment

Support researchers through concrete measures

- Align implementation of R&I grants to European practices
- Establish a supportive fund for R&I activities
- Set up regular data collection and provision under the Kosovo Research Information System

Increase international activities

- Develop a strategy to further improve participation in Horizon Europe
- Explore access to further European initiatives such as EURAXESS by improving national regulation and implementation practice
- Improve number of proposals and proposal success rate in Horizon Europe
- Establish active participation in ERA meetings and engage in the new European Innovation Agenda